

Pedagogical Strategies to Stimulate the Active Participation of Students in Mathematics Classes in Higher Education.

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Abstract

The most common pedagogical practice in teaching Basic Sciences in Engineering programs is the teacher-centered practice, which, through master classes, exposes the theoretical foundations and proposes exercises to strengthen students' knowledge. In these classroom environments, there are limited opportunities for student participation, and students must mostly attend to the teacher's explanations. Active learning pedagogical practices are often challenging to apply in this course. In this sense, at the University Institution of Envigado, we ask ourselves: How do we encourage evident student participation to identify progress in learning? The methodology used in this work is Critical Research (Skovsmose & Borba, 2004), in which three analytical situations are proposed: the current situation, the imagined situation (hypothetical situation or solution), and the fixed situation (realistic scenario of the imagined situation). Three negotiation processes: 1. pedagogical imagination, 2. practical organization, and 3. exploratory reasoning, make the three situations proposed in the model possible. In the current situation, it is identified that the generation of environments of trust fostered by the teacher, the generation of spaces for decision-making by the students, and the understanding of the subject are elements that encourage the participation of the students. However, these pedagogical strategies are not present in a generalized or structured way in all introductory science courses. In the imagined situation, pedagogical strategies are designed to increase the student's evident participation in classes. In this way, it is expected to generate an environment of trust that motivates the participation of students, changing their role as active agents in the learning process.

Keywords: Participation; Active Learning; Critical Research; Basic Sciences in Engineering.

1 Introduction

The Institución Universitaria de Envigado (IUE) has developed an action plan that seeks to carry out curricular transformations to align learning outcomes with the competencies and training profiles declared in the faculty programs. One of the institutional strategies outlined in this plan involves training teachers to design class activities that are truly aligned with the specific learning outcomes of each course. This process coincides with some situations identified by teachers of Basic Science courses associated with students' difficulties in understanding the concepts addressed, leading to limitations in their ability to analyze and interpret information or apply concepts in new contexts. As part of the institutional plan, several professors are sent to attend the New Alternatives in Engineering Education Course at Los Andes University, where the opportunity to rethink pedagogical practices in the Faculty of Engineering of the IUE is identified. Professors and researchers from both institutions materialize the intention to work on teaching transformation processes through the inter-institutional research project "Development and implementation of active methodologies in the area of the calculus of the Faculty of Engineering at the University Institution of Envigado" in which intervention strategies are designed to generate student-centered teaching processes for the courses Differential Calculus, Integral Calculus and Numerical Methods that are part of the basic cycle of the Electronic Engineering, Industrial Engineering and Computer Engineering programs.

This work is based on contemporary sociocultural educational theories and, therefore, emphasizes the importance of student participation in learning. In particular, it follows Wenger's approach (Wenger, 2001), where learning is assumed to be a social process that involves negotiating meanings. This process transforms the relationship between subjects and the world and simultaneously generates identity. It also considers the vision proposed by the theory of objectification (Radford, 2023), in which learning is understood as a collective cultural-historical process that creates spaces for construction between teacher and students in which both cooperate in different and complementary ways. On the other hand, students' participation in the class can be evidenced by cooperation and involvement, questioning, quality of answers, contribution of conclusions, and work in front of the class (Lo, 2010). Following objectification theory, actions demonstrating student participation should also involve elements such as identifying reflective subjects with critical positions in the face of mathematical discourses and practices to consider new possibilities for action and thought (Radford, 2023). Wenger refers to such participation as evident participation (Wenger, 2001).

Despite the results reported in a good number of studies related to the improvement of learning and knowledge retention (Handelsman et al., 2004), in general, there is considerable resistance to the implementation of active learning strategies in classes related to science education, as is the case of Basic Science courses at the IUE. According to (Handelsman et al., 2004), some university professors do not feel the need for change because current educational systems have produced excellent scientists, others are intimidated by the idea of implementing new pedagogical strategies, or they may even fear that identification as professors will affect their credibility as researchers.

Based on the above approaches, the team of researchers and professors participating in the inter-institutional research project developed at the IUE, whose objective is to transform pedagogical practices for the development of student-centered teaching-learning strategies in engineering programs, have formulated the research question: How to encourage the evident participation of students to identify progress in learning?

2 Critical Research

The research project uses the critical research methodology (Skovsmose & Borba, 2004) in which the transformation of pedagogical practices starts from the Current Situation in which those characteristics that occur in the classroom before the intervention are identified. Based on the theoretical constructs guiding the project, such as the conception of learning and the educational experience of researchers and teachers, intervention strategies are then designed, leading to the Imagined Situation. Implementing the strategies amid specific conditions and constraints results in a Fixed Situation that is not expected to coincide with the imagined situation.

Critical research is characterized by its interest in change, so it places particular emphasis on those things that do not happen in the classroom but could happen. This approach is especially interesting in the imagined situation because the construction carried out by researchers and professors mediates between current and fixed situations. The processes involved in transforming one situation into another allow us to understand the contributions of critical research. The process of pedagogical imagination offers the possibility of exploring conceptual alternatives to the current situation, thus generating an imagined situation. The process of Practical Organization includes all those actions and negotiations carried out by researchers, teachers, students, and administrators to implement the strategies designed in the imagined situation. However, for various reasons, these actions do not necessarily result in obtaining the imagined situation as designed, and practical organization can be described as "a realistic, and perhaps pragmatic, version of the pedagogical imagination" (Skovsmose & Borba, 2004, pp 208). Exploratory reasoning, on the other hand, allows us to analyze the

viability of the imagined situation based on the observations and evidence recorded in the arranged situation (See Figure 1).

Cooperation between researchers, teachers, students, and administrators is essential to carrying out each of the processes. Acknowledging cooperation in this way shows that in critical research, professors and students participate in research and do not become objects of investigation. This cooperative research is aligned with the socio-cultural theories of learning used as a reference for the pedagogical actions designed and implemented within the framework of the research project presented in this work.

In the research project developed at the IUE, the current situation is established from the records of observations in classes and surveys carried out during the 2023-1 semester to students in which it is sought to identify the level and type of participation that occurs in the classes, as well as the pedagogical strategies that generate it. At the beginning of the 2023-2 semester, a focus group was held with professors of some Basic Science subjects of the Engineering programs. Their perceptions of student participation in class are inquired about, and the records of observations and surveys are socialized. The activities and reflections carried out in this focus group give rise to imagined situations for each teacher based on the needs of their courses. After participating in the focus group, some teachers design intervention strategies to stimulate student class participation. At the end of the 2023-2 semester, a new focus group is held where teachers socialize their fixed situations and the observations made in implementing the designed strategies.

Figure 1. Critical Research Model, adapted from the figure presented by Skovsmove and Borba (2004).

3 Current situation

The introductory science courses of the Faculty of Engineering at the IUE use a traditional approach in which the detailed planning of the contents leads each teacher to use a master methodology to complete the objectives established for each class. Observations of classes from three different courses carried out during the 2023-1 semester allow us to identify two moments as common elements of the classes: the first moment corresponds to the explanation of the fundamental concepts of the theory, followed by the second moment in which the consolidation of the contents takes place by solving exercises that the teacher considers representative (Bustamante et al., 2023).

From the systematization of the observations, it is possible to describe the characteristic elements of the class environment in the groups. In the first moment of class, where the theoretical foundations and the steps to follow in the solution procedures are described, the students are attentive and take notes of the explanation the teacher writes on the board. The teacher often asks the students questions to assess their level of attention and comprehension of the explanations or prior knowledge. These questions result in short and often incomplete answers from some students. In the second stage, the students ask questions mainly related to the aspects of the solution procedures presented that are confusing for them. Sporadically, the teacher proposes activities to the students, such as going to the board to solve exercises or doing some work in teams during class. The teacher complements these activities with exercises assigned to the students so they can solve them outside the class and prepare them for the evaluation activities, which are primarily written and individual. The participation of the students is minor and is not necessarily generated by the activities proposed by the teacher. No significant changes were observed in the quantity or quality of the participations in the groups observed.

At the end of the 2023-1 semester, students were surveyed, and they were asked about their level of participation, how they participated, motivations, and barriers they identified to participate (Bustamante et al., 2023). From this information, it was concluded that the participation of the students consists firstly of *asking about the aspects that they do not understand of what the teacher explains, and secondly, of developing the class activities*. The option: *I do not usually participate in classes* ranked third, while the option *Propose alternative solutions to problems posed by the teacher* ranked fourth. The three main motivations for participating in class chosen by the students are in their order: *Understanding the topic being discussed in class, the usefulness or application of the topics, and class activities that invite participation*. On the other hand, the three main reasons that discourage student participation in class are *Not understanding the topic being discussed in class, The possibility of being questioned by classmates or the teacher, and A teacher's language that can become very technical*. These responses summarize the barriers students identify to participating in class activities. (¿Incluimos un enlace a la encuesta?)

However, in one of the groups observed, students showed greater participation, generating a classroom environment conducive to student-centered teaching. Within this group, students were actively engaged in asking questions, proposing alternative solutions, discussing exercise solutions, suggesting modifications, and taking the initiative to go to the board to perform specific procedures. The records of the observations make it possible to identify actions in the teacher that encourage student participation. The teacher is empathetic, which helps to build the confidence of the students in the class; he constantly asks them to select exercises to solve, making them an active part of the development of the class and recognizes the results obtained in the activities with which he stimulates the students to continue advancing in the assigned exercises.

The group of professors-researchers was concerned about what was happening in the classes of the professors who were not participating in the research. Therefore, it was decided to hold a focus group with all the professors at the beginning of the 2023-2 semester. In this focus group, similarities were identified in teaching methodologies, class moments, assessment practices, and student behavior in terms of class participation. The conversation started by investigating the teachers' perception of their students' class participation. Most of them stated that it was low and that it was challenging to generate it. They used statements such as: *"Students do not show a willingness to solve problems on the board"* and *"They do not share their doubts with the group or with the teacher during class, although the teacher provides a space to discuss them"*. One of the teachers says that *"when some kind of challenge is raised, the students react"*. For instance, this teacher assigns a bonus in a written assessment to the student who solves an exercise proposed in class. The professor adds, *"If an exercise is proposed without giving some kind of prize, no one leaves"* and concludes, *"Motivation starts with bonuses"*. Another professor points out that *"the little participation in my classes generally comes from the same two or three students, although on some occasions these participations encourage other students to participate as well."*

For a third teacher, student engagement increases as they progress through their training. Teacher number four says, "When explaining some kind of exercise, I tend to intentionally make errors when explaining an exercise to expect some kind of intervention from the students. This has helped me a lot in my practice because I can identify whether those present are attentive or not." Teacher number 3 participates again in the conversation to point out two aspects. He highlights the importance of empathy with her students and assumes it is the act of working on self-esteem by getting emotionally close to her students. He ends by saying, "Most of my students complete their work not because they want to learn more, but simply to fulfill a duty". These perceptions of teachers are consistent with student survey results and confirm student engagement orientation.

The observations are made in a group of each course. The characteristics of the students in each group are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Characteristics of observed groups.

Observed group	Semester	Class schedule	Number of students	Number of observed classes.
Differential Calculus	2	Daytime	32	5
Integral Calculus	3	Daytime	18	4
Numerical Methods	5	Daytime	18	6

The IUE offers students two types of class schedules, daytime and nocturnal, which determine the schedules of the courses. In the daytime option, courses are offered between 8 am and 6 pm. In the nocturnal option, the courses can be enrolled between 6 am and 8 am or between 6 pm and 10 pm. All the groups observed correspond to the daytime option. The nocturnal option is designed for those students who are working, so it is expected that these students will be older than those in the daytime option, have less time available for their studies and be enrolled in the last semesters of their programs. Unlike the observations, the survey was carried out in all the groups of the courses Differential Calculus, Integral Calculus and Numerical Methods.

In conclusion of this current situation, teachers have noticed that only a few students are participating in the classes and some pedagogical strategies that promote participation are associated with the assignment of rewards to improve the results of individual written exams. Moreover, class activities correspond not necessarily to a particular conception of learning but rather to factors such as student attention during teacher explanations. This current situation and the reflections made by researchers and teachers lead to the research question: How can the evident participation of students be encouraged to identify progress in learning?

4 Imagined situation and pedagogical imagination.

The imagined situation arises from the process of pedagogical imagination. This process enables teachers to challenge the exercise of conceptualizing the possibilities of change in the classroom "because the existence of alternatives shows that the current situation is not a necessity" (Skovsmose & Borba, 2004, p. 208). The pedagogical imagination involves sociocultural knowing and knowledge present in the teaching-learning process, such as the teacher's understanding of the notion of learning, their knowledge about the students' educational particularities, and their knowledge about previous educational experiences.

Based on the reflections in the first focus group, the results of the class observations, surveys, and some of the theoretical concepts mentioned earlier in this work, the teachers are invited to implement actions that promote their students' participation. They are asked to record the participation generated in the classes to identify its impact on the learning processes. Reviewing the theoretical foundations of the project with the teachers of the

focus group means that, in addition to the teaching experience, the pedagogical imagination involves conceptual elements that show that other situations are possible.

At the end of the focus group, several teachers expressed their intention to implement an intervention strategy, which allowed the teachers to identify the imagined situation. A first teacher admits to having difficulties getting closer to his students, so he decides to work on developing strategies that improve his empathy with the group. A second teacher shows interest in implementing strategies that include students in class decision-making, so he mentions the possibilities of proposing problems in the classroom and allowing students to select based on their interests. He even considers discussing with his students how to do some other class activities. Two professors expressed their intention to use collaborative work activities in the classes after reflecting on the concept of learning based on contemporary socio-cultural theories and understanding the need to promote a cooperative construction. The reflections made in this group are conversations in which the other teachers and researchers help each teacher clarify their imagined situation based on their experiences and knowledge of educational issues. As Skovsmose points out, the imagined situation occurs amid cooperative work based on negotiation processes, like the other situations.

5 Fixed situation and practical organization.

No meetings were held with professors during the 2023-2 semester. Each teacher carried out the monitoring of the intervention strategies through the observation of class dynamics, the photographic record in some cases and the construction of a field diary in others. At the end of the semester, a second focus group was held to learn about the results of the teachers' observation exercises and the possible implementation of strategies to encourage participation. The teachers agree that the exercise of the first focus group made them transform their methodology and the way they selected class activities because there was now an intention to generate participation.

The first teacher stated, *"From the previous meeting, I was very impressed by aspects related to empathy because that is complicated for me because affinity is more with some students than others, but now I try to get closer to other students. Now, I try to be attentive throughout the classroom and get everyone involved in the class dynamics. I am thinking, for example, of my Differential Calculus course because it is the one in which I have noticed the most changes, and it is the one in which I found it most particular that this semester has been different like they have studied. In this group, I have seen a greater willingness to participate than in others I have had."* The second teacher mentions: *"With some activities, such as allowing them to choose the exercises to do in class, the position of some changed"*.

A third teacher shares his experience in which he decided to implement collaborative work in his classes. *"I started proposing group assignments in class, and the participation increased, even from students who previously did not. Teamwork has led some students to take a leading role in explaining the solution procedures to their classmates."* This activity changed the teacher's view of his students because, before this, he perceived apathy among some students who took an active role in collaborative work activities.

A fourth teacher also implements collaborative work activities in his classes, proposing exercises to be discussed and solved in teams. Some of the professor's conclusions are: *"I have observed that if collaborative work activities are carried out sustainably in several classes, spaces for discussion and reflection are fostered. I used to propose activities in teams to solve exercises years ago. However, without the look of collaborative work, I was frustrated to observe that most students wasted time doing things different from the proposals. I designed class activities this semester regarding the students' expected learning. This new approach makes that most of them use all the time in the class to work on the proposed activities"*. Regarding teamwork, the professor

indicates: *"The discussions are fascinating because they allow us to identify the students' gaps, the aspects that represent the greatest difficulty for them and the aspects that are being understood. I have understood that an attentive student in class is not necessarily learning, and more so, it is unclear to me what they understand and do not."* The professor adds, *"I have noticed that some students understand topics better with their classmates' explanations than with me."* In this case, collaborative work has led to spaces for participation in each team, which often becomes a general participation with discussions that involve all students.

The professor who led the group where student participation was observed expressed frustration. He could not obtain the same level of participation with a group in the 2023-2 semester. This group has 30 students enrolled, and the professor has used the same strategies that worked previously. However, in the group that showed successful pedagogical strategies, only 17 students were enrolled, making it easier to encourage student participation. The teacher's methodology encourages participation in his groups, which means that, unlike other teachers, he is struck by the fact that he does not have participatory classes. In the description of his successful experiences, the professor refers to the feeling of *"loss of control"* generated by participatory groups: *"Sometimes losing control is not bad, that is, losing control from the planning that is done is not so bad because there are classes that even when they are not within the planning that has been done for the day, They are very productive classes because the students themselves kind of direct it to what they have doubts, to what they need to learn and then you think I went through the class solving those doubts and I did not do the class."* The teacher's description shows that the student's participation does not occur from the teacher's planning but from how much they consider that their learning needs can be met.

6 Exploratory reasoning and conclusions

The team of researchers and professors of the research project shared with the professors attending the focus group examples of actions carried out by other professors from the same faculty that encouraged participation in classes. Likewise, the results of the observations made in several groups and the surveys applied to students of Differential Calculus, Integral Calculus, and Numerical Methods were socialized. The information shared generated the conditions for a situation imagined in the specific conditions of each teacher. The reflections made in the first focus group showed the teachers that the activities planned for the classes do not necessarily encourage student participation so, according to the learning approach defined in this work, learning is not necessarily being generated. Teachers recognize that the few actions of students in classes have an extrinsic motivation associated with an interest in improving grades.

The teachers have not considered the importance of student participation in the teaching-learning process, which shows that this group of teachers has not reflected on what should be understood by learning. Consequently, class activities are not student-centered. Class observations and focus groups may even suggest that class activities are content-focused because some teachers express discomfort with the amount of content associated with each course, meaning they have to allocate less time than they consider necessary to address each topic in the class. The discussions generated in the first focus group fostered spaces of pedagogical imagination based on negotiation between teachers that led each teacher to select an intervention strategy.

In the second focus group, teachers share their observations. Despite not carrying out rigorous processes of recording information in the classes, their observations on the student's response to the proposed strategy show that there is an increase in the quantity and quality of participation in each intervention. Although some strategies had better results than others, with all of them, students began to mobilize, and some teachers could consider new pedagogical strategies because they observed evident changes in the classroom environment.

The pedagogical imagination produces a noticeable change between the current situation, in which the participation of a few students motivated by the intention of improving grades in the course is expected, and that obtained in the fixed situation, in which students are reported to participate in classes motivated by feeling included in the selection of class activities or because they feel comfortable in small work groups, or even, they feel in an environment of trust as a result of a teacher who works on improving their empathy with the group of students. The teachers' observations mention participations that generate greater integration and students who explain processes to others, which shows that more intentional actions on the part of teachers lead to different results, and this is possible in mathematics classes without losing the rigor in the processes.

During the 2023-2 semester, the professors who decided to intervene in their groups designed pedagogical strategies autonomously, based on the discussions held in the first focus group, and applied them at the time they considered appropriate. Among other reasons, the fact that they were not part of the research project team made it difficult to generate spaces for conversation that would allow them to follow up on these actions and enable additional negotiation and feedback processes. This partly explains that the results shared by the teachers in the second focus group reflect activities carried out in one or more classes, which does not allow for a new classroom environment. Nonetheless, this experience offers an opportunity to transform some pedagogical practices if the process described in this work continues rigorously and sustainably over time.

7 References

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